

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

On the pore geometry and structure rock typing

Published in *ACS Omega*, July, 2024, DOI Link: <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.4c02879>

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Supplementary Information emphasises: i) Detailed derivations (**Appendices A to E**) and ii) The effects of varied specific surface area S_s and tortuosity τ onto the Pore Geometry and Structure (PGS) Rock Type (**Appendix F**). Detailed derivations encompass: i) Permeability derivation from Newton’s viscosity law and capillary bundled model (**Appendix A**), ii) Definition of specific surface area (**Appendix B**), iii) Kozeny-Carman equation (**Appendix C**), iv) Electrical conductivity in wet porous media modelled as parallel circuits (**Appendix D**), and v) Permeability fitting using PGS parameters (**Appendix E**).

Permeability in **Appendix F** is computed with Kozeny-Carman equation and porosity ranges 0.01-0.99. Matlab code to generate plots in **Appendix F** are available. We also provide all data for main figures that appear in our manuscript (Data for Figures.xlsx).

Repository link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12817855>

Repository at NYCU Dataverse: <https://doi.org/10.57770/SCMDDF>

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APPENDICES

1. Appendix A: Permeability

Newton's Viscosity Law expresses that viscosity μ is a measure of its resistance to deforming at a certain shear rate dv/dr and the fluid deformation itself is due to a shear stress τ_D constituted by the drag force F_D working on a tangential surface S_p along the pipe with a length of ℓ :

$$\tau_D \equiv \frac{F_D}{S_p} = -\mu \frac{dv}{dr} \quad [\text{A-1a}]$$

$$\frac{\Delta P \cdot A_C}{2\pi r \ell} = -\mu \frac{dv}{dr} \quad [\text{A-1b}]$$

$$\frac{\Delta P \cdot \pi r^2}{2\pi r \ell} = -\mu \frac{dv}{dr} \quad [\text{A-1c}]$$

The drag force F_D is quantifiable through a given pressure drop ΔP working on a cross-sectional area A_C . The tangential shear stress τ_D would resist the fluid flow and hinder velocity v across the radius of pipe r . The negative sign denotes the reduction of velocity with the growth of radius from the centre of the pipe. Note: vectors of v and r are perpendicular (Figure S 1).

Figure S 1. Illustration of fluid flow in the pore. The drag force F_D on cylindrical pore with a length of ℓ . The distribution of velocity v decreases as the radius r reaches the edge of pipe at R .

Assign $v = 0$ at the pipe edge ($r = R$) and $v = v_{max}$ at the center of the pipe ($r = 0$).

Therefore, we have velocity v at an arbitrary r derived as follows

$$\int_R^r -\frac{\Delta P r}{2\ell\mu} dr = \int_0^v dv \quad [\text{A-2a}]$$

$$-\frac{\Delta P}{2\ell\mu} \frac{(r^2 - R^2)}{2} = v \quad [\text{A-2b}]$$

$$v = \frac{\Delta P}{4\mu\ell} (R^2 - r^2) \quad [\text{A-2c}]$$

Compute the volumetric rate q passing through into a pipe with a cross-sectional area A_C :

$$q = \int v dA_C = \int_0^R \frac{\Delta P}{4\mu\ell} (R^2 - r^2) 2\pi r dr \quad [\text{A-3a}]$$

$$q = \frac{\pi\Delta P}{2\mu\ell} \int_0^R R^2 \cdot r - r^3 dr \quad [\text{A-3b}]$$

$$q = \frac{\pi\Delta P}{2\mu\ell} \left[\frac{R^2 r^2}{2} - \frac{r^4}{4} \right]_0^R \quad [\text{A-3c}]$$

$$q = \frac{\pi\Delta P}{8\mu\ell} R^4 \quad [\text{A-3d}]$$

We call Eq. A-3d as Hagen–Poiseuille equation. Tortuosity τ is the ratio between fluid path ℓ and the straight bulk length L , which has a dimensionless unit and typical values of

$$\tau \equiv \frac{\ell}{L} \geq 1 \quad [\text{A-4}]$$

There are N numbers of bundled pipes that contribute to the total rate Q passing through the rock:

$$Q = Nq = N \left(\frac{\pi\Delta P}{8\mu\ell} R^4 \right) \quad [\text{A-5a}]$$

$$Q = \frac{N\pi\Delta PR^4}{8\mu\tau L} \quad [\text{A-5b}]$$

$$Q = \frac{N\pi R^4 \Delta P}{8\mu\tau L} \quad [\text{A-5c}]$$

$$Q = N\pi R^2 \tau \frac{R^2}{8\mu\tau^2} \frac{dP}{dx} \quad [\text{A-5d}]$$

Note: Suppose $\frac{\Delta P}{L}$ is equivalent to a pressure gradient $\frac{dP}{dx}$. Recall the definition of porosity ϕ to

define the bulk crosssectional area A :

$$\phi = \frac{V_{pore}}{V_{bulk}} = \frac{N\pi R^2 \ell}{A \cdot L} = \frac{N\pi R^2}{A} \cdot \tau \quad [\text{A-6a}]$$

$$N\pi R^2 \tau = \phi A \quad [\text{A-6b}]$$

Arrange Eq. A-5d using A-6b, such that

$$Q = \phi A \frac{R^2}{8\mu\tau^2} \frac{dP}{dx} \rightarrow Q = \frac{\phi R^2}{8\tau^2} \frac{A}{\mu} \frac{dP}{dx} \quad [\text{A-7}]$$

Recall the definition of Darcy's equation:

$$Q = k \frac{A}{\mu} \frac{dP}{dx} \quad [\text{A-8}]$$

Then, equate the formulations in Eq. A-7 and A-8; therefore, the absolute permeability k equals to be

$$k \equiv \frac{\phi R^2}{8\tau^2} \quad [\text{A-9a}]$$

$$k \equiv \frac{\phi d^2}{32\tau^2} \quad [\text{A-9b}]$$

Note: The d is the pore diameter. The dimension of absolute permeability k is $[\text{L}^2]$ with the unit of m^2 , Darcy, or milli-Darcy mD.

We will derive the conversion of permeability in petroleum engineering k into geotechnical or civil engineering's permeability, known as hydraulic conductivity k_h , with the dimension of [L/T] or unit of cm/s or m/s. The total fluid velocity v_T in porous media is driven by the total head gradient $i \equiv dh/dx$ through a geomaterial with a hydraulic conductivity k_h :

$$v_T = k_h i \quad [\text{A-10}]$$

The studied liquid in geotechnical engineering is mainly water. So, it is not important to explicitly state the viscosity μ . Recall Q in Eq. A-8 to be

$$Q = v_T A \rightarrow v_T = \frac{k dP}{\mu dx} \quad [\text{A-11a}]$$

Recall the definition of static pressure $P = \rho g h$ and the total head gradient $i = dh/dx$. Then, equate the petroleum engineering version on the left-hand-side with the geotechnical engineering version on the right-hand-side:

$$\frac{k dP}{\mu dx} = k_h i \quad [\text{A-12a}]$$

$$\frac{k}{\mu} \rho g \frac{dh}{dx} = k_h \frac{dh}{dx} \quad [\text{A-12b}]$$

$$k = k_h \frac{\mu}{\rho g} \quad [\text{A-12c}]$$

Note that viscosity μ has a unit of mPa.s and dimension of [ML⁻¹T⁻¹]. Thus, we can convert the hydraulic conductivity k_h [LT⁻¹] into permeability k [L²] using Eq. A-12c (unit in m²). Then, we need the value of 0.9869233×10⁻¹² m²/D to convert into Darcy or 9.869233×10⁻¹⁶ m²/mD (milli-Darcy).

2. Appendix B: Specific surface area

Volumetric specific surface area S_V [1/m] or [1/cm] is defined as

$$S_V = \frac{\text{Inner Surface Area}}{\text{Bulk Volume}} \quad [\text{B-1a}]$$

$$S_V = \frac{S}{V_T} \quad [\text{B-1b}]$$

$$S_V = \frac{N \cdot 2\pi R \cdot \ell}{A \cdot L} \quad [\text{B-1c}]$$

$$S_V = \frac{N2\pi R\tau}{A} \quad [\text{B-1d}]$$

$$S_V = 2 \frac{N\pi R^2\tau}{A} \frac{1}{R} \quad [\text{B-1e}]$$

The substitution of $N\pi R^2\tau$ in Eq. A-6b into B-1e results in

$$S_V = 2 \frac{\phi A}{A} \frac{1}{R} \quad [\text{B-2a}]$$

$$S_V = \frac{2\phi}{R} \quad [\text{B-2b}]$$

Gravimetric specific surface area S_S [m^2/g], also just called Specific surface with a known mineral density ρ_m is defined as follows:

$$S_S \equiv \frac{\text{Inner Surface Area}}{\text{Solid Grain Mass}} \quad [\text{B-3a}]$$

$$S_S = \frac{S}{\rho_m V_m} \quad [\text{B-3b}]$$

$$S_S = \frac{S}{\rho_m (V_T - V_P)} \quad [\text{B-3c}]$$

$$S_S = \frac{S}{\rho_m (1 - \phi)} \quad [\text{B-3d}]$$

$$S_S = \frac{1}{1 - \phi} \frac{S_V}{\rho_m} \quad [\text{B-3e}]$$

$$S_S = \frac{1}{1 - \phi} \frac{2\phi}{\rho_m R} \quad [\text{B-3f}]$$

We evaluate a volumetric composition of mineral V_m that is obtained from total V_T and subtracted by pore volume V_p . Substitute Eq. B-2b into B-3e in the process of derivation. Some works come up with the terminology of volumetric grain specific surface S_{Vg} , which is an analogue of S_S (Eq. B-3f):

$$S_{Vg} \equiv \frac{\text{Inner Surface Area}}{\text{Solid Grain Volume}} \quad [\text{B-4a}]$$

$$S_{Vg} = \frac{S}{V_m} \quad [\text{B-4b}]$$

$$S_{Vg} = \rho_m S_S \quad [\text{B-4c}]$$

$$S_{Vg} = \frac{1}{1 - \phi} \frac{2\phi}{R} \quad [\text{B-4d}]$$

Next, let us derive another form of a specific surface S_S according to the physical structures of the mineral, for example, a long platy mineral as depicted in Figure S 2.

Figure S 2. Depiction of platy minerals to illustrate parallel clay.

Suppose $p > l \gg t$ which results in $1/t \gg 1/l > 1/p$, thereby the S_S is

$$S_S \equiv \frac{\text{Surface Area}}{\text{Solid Grain Mass}} \quad [\text{B-5a}]$$

$$S_S = \frac{2(pl + pt + lt)}{\rho_m(plt)} = \frac{2}{\rho_m} \left(\frac{1}{t} + \frac{1}{l} + \frac{1}{p} \right) \quad [\text{B-5b}]$$

$$S_S \approx \frac{2}{\rho_m t} \quad [\text{B-5c}]$$

Assume the structure is formed by a few platy minerals, i.e., parallel sheets. Therefore, the porosity and pore space d_p established in the parallel sheet emerge to be

$$\phi = \frac{d_p}{d_p + t} \rightarrow d_p = \frac{\phi}{1 - \phi} t \quad [\text{B-6}]$$

Input the mineral thickness t from Eq. B-5c into Eq. B-6. Accordingly, the pore space in the parallel sheet d_p is then defined as

$$d_p = \frac{\phi}{1 - \phi} \frac{2}{\rho_m S_S} \quad [\text{B-7}]$$

We recall B-3f in diameter variable $d = 2R$ (cylindrical pore) to be

$$d = \frac{\phi}{1 - \phi} \frac{4}{\rho_m S_S} \quad [\text{B-8}]$$

See the comparison between Eqs. B-7 and B-8 designate parallel sheet vs cylindrical pores. We can generalise the factors of 2 (parallel sheet) or 4 (cylindrical) to be the geometrical factor α as in the pore diameter

$$d = \frac{\phi}{1 - \phi} \frac{\alpha}{\rho_m S_S} \quad [\text{B-9}]$$

3. Appendix C: Kozeny-Carman equation

The substitution of $R = f(S_V)$ from Eq. B-2b, $R = f(S_S)$ from Eq. B-3f, and $d = f(S_S, \alpha)$ from Eq. B-9 into the definition of permeability k (Eq. A-9a) yields in the Kozeny-Carman equation in these forms:

$$k = \frac{\phi}{8\tau^2} \left(\frac{2\phi}{S_V} \right)^2 = \frac{\phi^3}{2\tau^2 S_V^2} \quad [\text{C-1}]$$

$$k = \frac{\phi}{8\tau^2} \left(\frac{1}{1-\phi} \frac{2\phi}{\rho_m S_S} \right)^2 = \frac{\phi^3}{2(1-\phi)^2 \tau^2 \rho_m^2 S_S^2} \quad [\text{C-2}]$$

$$k = \frac{\phi}{32\tau^2} \left(\frac{\phi}{1-\phi} \frac{\alpha}{\rho_m S_S} \right)^2 = \frac{\phi^3}{32(1-\phi)^2 \tau^2 \rho_m^2 S_S^2} \quad [\text{C-3}]$$

We will compare the Kozeny-Carman equation in petroleum and geotechnical engineering. The equation in geotechnical engineering is presented as follows ¹:

$$k_h = \frac{e^3}{1+e} \frac{C_F g}{v_f} \frac{1}{\rho_m^2 S_S^2} \quad [\text{C-4a}]$$

Convert the hydraulic conductivity in geotechnical engineering k_h into petroleum engineering k (Eq. A-12c); alter the void ratio e into porosity ϕ with the relationship of $e = \phi/(1-\phi)$, and expand the kinematic fluid viscosity v_f to a dynamic fluid viscosity $\mu = \rho v_f$; those lead to

$$\frac{k\rho g}{\mu} = \frac{\phi^3/(1-\phi)^3}{1 + \frac{\phi}{1-\phi}} \frac{C_F g}{\mu/\rho} \frac{1}{\rho_m^2 S_S^2} \quad [\text{C-4b}]$$

$$k = C_F \frac{\phi^3}{(1-\phi)^2} \frac{1}{\rho_m^2 S_S^2} \quad [\text{C-4c}]$$

Later, compare Eqs. C-2 and C-4c, which results in

$$C_F = \frac{1}{2\tau^2} \quad [\text{C-5}]$$

The value of pore topology constant C_F of 0.2 ^{1,2} suggests that the tortuosity of soil samples τ is around 1.58.

If we move a porosity variable ϕ into the left-hand side of Eq. C-2 and then perform square root operation, we get the concept of hydraulic flow unit HFU:

$$\sqrt{\frac{k}{\phi}} = \frac{\phi}{(1-\phi)} \times \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}\tau\rho_m S_S} \quad [\text{C-6a}]$$

$$RQI = \phi_Z \times FZI \quad [\text{C-6b}]$$

The HFU concept consists of Reservoir Quality Index RQI , normalised porosity ϕ_Z , and flow zone indicator FZI . This concept is just the way to plot where the FZI is not explicitly calculated from τ , ρ_m , and S_S but rather RQI/ϕ_Z . Note: the unit of k in Eq. C-6a is m^2 .

4. Appendix D: Electrical conductivity

Suppose the value of one is expandable to a ratio of volume to volume:

$$1 = \frac{AL}{V_T} = \frac{A_f L_f}{V_f} = \frac{A_m L_m}{V_m} = \frac{A_S L_S}{V_S} \quad [\text{D-1}]$$

where the subscript T : total or bulk, f : fluid, m : mineral, and S : surface. Note that the volume is approached with a tube model with a cross-sectional area A and length L . Recall the definition of the resistance-resistivity R - ρ which is equivalent to conductance-conductivity G - σ :

$$R = \frac{L}{A} \rho \quad [\text{D-2a}]$$

$$G = \frac{A}{L} \sigma \quad [\text{D-2b}]$$

Electronic conductions in solid minerals, ionic conductions in pore fluid, and counter-ion transports due to mineral-fluid interactions can be modelled as a parallel circuit if each phenomenon is in the parallel orientation within the applied electrical field³⁻⁵. We use the basic equation (Eq. D-2) to model the parallel circuit among the fluid, mineral and surface components:

$$\frac{1}{R_T} = \frac{1}{R_f} + \frac{1}{R_m} + \frac{1}{R_S} \quad [\text{D-3a}]$$

$$G_T = G_f + G_m + G_S \quad [\text{D-3b}]$$

$$\sigma_T \frac{A}{L} = \sigma_f \frac{A_f}{L_f} + \sigma_m \frac{A_m}{L_m} + \sigma_S \frac{A_S}{L_S} \quad [\text{D-3c}]$$

$$\sigma_T = \sigma_f \frac{A_f L}{A L_f} + \sigma_m \frac{A_m L}{A L_m} + \sigma_S \frac{A_S L}{A L_S} \quad [\text{D-3d}]$$

Suppose the tube length over the bulk length is defined as the tortuosity τ . The expression of surface-related cross-sectional area A_S is constructed from the diffuse double layer with the thickness of λ and covers along the pore perimeter $2\pi r$ (Figure S 3). Together with the definition of A_S , substitute Eq. D-1 into Eq. D-3d to obtain this set of equations:

$$\sigma_T = \sigma_f \frac{V_f L}{V_T L_f} + \sigma_m \frac{V_m L}{V_T L_m} + \sigma_S \frac{2\pi r \lambda L}{A L_S} \quad [\text{D-4a}]$$

$$\sigma_T = \sigma_f \frac{V_f V_p}{V_p V_T \tau_f^2} + \sigma_m (1 - \phi) \frac{1}{\tau_m^2} + \sigma_S \frac{\lambda 2\pi r L_S}{A L_S} \frac{L}{L_S} \quad [\text{D-4b}]$$

$$\sigma_T = \sigma_f S_f \phi \frac{1}{\tau_f^2} + \sigma_m (1 - \phi) \frac{1}{\tau_m^2} + \sigma_S \frac{\lambda S}{A L_S^2} \frac{L}{L_S} \quad [\text{D-4c}]$$

Figure S 3. Double layer λ emergence between the bulk pore fluid and solid surface. The thickness of $\lambda \ll r$ hence we can assume that r is the distance of solid surface to the centre of pore.

The internal surface S can be described with $S = S_S \rho_m V_m = S_S \rho_m (1 - \phi) V_T$. Then, expand the $V_T = AL$; therefore,

$$\sigma_T = \sigma_f S_f \phi \frac{1}{\tau_f^2} + \sigma_m (1 - \phi) \frac{1}{\tau_m^2} + \sigma_S \frac{\lambda}{A} S_S \rho_m (1 - \phi) V_T \frac{L}{L_S^2} \quad [\text{D-5a}]$$

$$\sigma_T = \sigma_f S_f \phi \frac{1}{\tau_f^2} + \sigma_m (1 - \phi) \frac{1}{\tau_m^2} + \sigma_S \frac{\lambda}{A} S_S \rho_m (1 - \phi) (AL) \frac{L}{L_S^2} \quad [\text{D-5b}]$$

$$\sigma_T = \sigma_f S_f \phi \frac{1}{\tau_f^2} + \sigma_m (1 - \phi) \frac{1}{\tau_m^2} + \sigma_S \lambda S_S \rho_m (1 - \phi) \frac{1}{\tau_S^2} \quad [\text{D-5c}]$$

The thickness of diffuse double layer λ could be approached by the Debye-Huckel characteristic length ⁶:

$$\lambda = \sqrt{\frac{\kappa' \epsilon_0 k T}{2 N_A e^2 I}} \quad [\text{D-6a}]$$

$$I = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N c_i z_i^2 \quad [\text{D-6b}]$$

with the associated variables are bulk fluid relative permittivity κ' , vacuum permittivity ϵ_0 , Boltzmann constant k , temperature T , Avogadro number N_A , elementary charge e , ionic strength I , the concentration of each ion c_i , and valence number z_i .

We simplify the form of Eq. D-5c with assumed tortuosity $\tau_m = \tau_f = 1$, generally called as τ , and define a surface conduction factor $\Gamma = \sigma_S \lambda \rho_m / \tau_S^2$:

$$\sigma_T = \sigma_f S_f \phi + (\sigma_m + \Gamma S_S) (1 - \phi) \quad [\text{D-7}]$$

In the clayey sample, the contribution of S_S is huge compared to σ_f and the mineral conductivity is minute, $\sigma_m \ll \sigma_T$.

The first term of Eq. D-5c prevails in a clean sample, which we name Archie's equation 7,8:

$$\sigma_T = \sigma_f S_f \frac{\phi}{\tau^2} \quad [\text{D-8a}]$$

$$\sigma_T = \sigma_f S_f^{n_A} \frac{\phi^{m_A}}{a_t} \quad [\text{D-8b}]$$

and we use arbitrary positive constants m_A and n_A (Eq. D-8b) to fit the data and accommodate the surface conduction (2nd term of Eq. D-7). We call the squared-tortuosity τ^2 as the tortuosity factor $a_t > 0$. Saturated sample $S_f = 1$ alters Archie's equation to be

$$\sigma_T = \sigma_f \frac{\phi^{m_A}}{a_t} \quad [\text{D-9}]$$

Further, we define the formation factor F as

$$F \equiv \frac{\sigma_f}{\sigma_T} \equiv \frac{\rho_T}{\rho_f} = a_t \phi^{-m_A} \quad [\text{D-10}]$$

where $m_A > 0$. Note: electrical conductivity σ [S/m] is the reciprocal of resistivity ρ [$\Omega \cdot \text{m}$].

5. Appendix E: PGS Permeability fitting

The pore geometry and structure (PGS) concept is defined as the plot between $\sqrt{\frac{k}{\phi}}$ and $\frac{k}{\phi^3}$ that is connected by positive constants of a and b :

$$\sqrt{\frac{k}{\phi}} = a \left(\frac{k}{\phi^3} \right)^b \quad [\text{E-1}]$$

We will show the derivation of permeability prediction formulation using PGS constants a and b . The fitting method consists of two other constants m and n which correlate the water

saturation S_w and measured permeability k . The predicted permeability \hat{k} indeed uses a recursive method and non-explicitly forward model:

$$\hat{k} = f(k, \phi, S_w) \quad [\text{E-2}]$$

The following derivations detail formulations derived from routine core analysis RCA and special core analysis SCA data. The data derived from the SCA technique provides a negative slope $-n$ between the (irreducible) water saturation S_w and measured permeability k ^{9,10}:

$$S_w = mk^{-n} \rightarrow k = \left(\frac{S_w}{m}\right)^{-\frac{1}{n}} = \left(\frac{m}{S_w}\right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \quad [\text{E-3}]$$

We set constants m and n as positive values. Substitution of Eq. E-3 into the left-hand side of Eq. E-1 results in

$$\sqrt{\frac{\left(\frac{m}{S_w}\right)^{\frac{1}{n}}}{\phi}} = a \left(\frac{k}{\phi^3}\right)^b \quad [\text{E-4}]$$

The b -th root operation on both sides yields in

$$\begin{aligned} k &= \frac{1}{a^{\frac{1}{b}}} \left[\frac{\left(\frac{m}{S_w}\right)^{\frac{1}{n}}}{\phi} \right]^{\frac{1}{2b}} \phi^3 = \frac{1}{a^{\frac{1}{b}}} \left(\frac{m}{S_w}\right)^{\frac{1}{2nb}} \phi^{3-\frac{1}{2b}} = \frac{1}{a^{\frac{1}{b}}} \left(\frac{m}{S_w}\right)^{\frac{1}{2nb}} \phi^{\frac{6b-1}{2b}} \\ &= \frac{m^{\frac{1}{2nb}}}{a^{\frac{1}{b}}} \left(S_w^{-\frac{1}{n}} \phi^{6b-1}\right)^{\frac{1}{2b}} = \left(\frac{m^{\frac{1}{2n}}}{a}\right)^{\frac{1}{b}} \frac{\phi^{3-\frac{1}{2b}}}{S_w^{\frac{1}{2nb}}} \end{aligned} \quad [\text{E-5}]$$

Rearrange Eq. E-5 to state the predicted permeability \hat{k} explicitly:

$$\hat{k} = p \left(\frac{1}{\phi^q S_w^r} \right)^s; \quad p = \left(\frac{m^{1/2n}}{a} \right)^{\frac{1}{b}}; \quad q = \frac{1}{2b} - 3; \quad r = \frac{1}{2nb}; \quad s = 1 \quad [\text{E-6}]$$

Note: the constants $\{a, b\}$ are from RCA data, while $\{m, n\}$ are from SCA tests.

6. Appendix F: Effects of specific surface area and tortuosity onto the PGS Rock Type

Figure S 4. Conventional permeability-porosity cross-plot with known PGS rock type RT lines. PGS stands for the Pore Geometry and Structure. Permeability is computed from the Kozeny-Carman equations with porosity from 0.0001 to 0.99. Circles are to show the intersection points. Symbol of S_s for specific surface area.

Figure S 5. PGS plot with known tortuosity and specific surface area. Each circle is from the intersection points between lines in Figure S 4. Part (a) showing all typical tortuosities. Part (b) emphasizes the distribution of specific surface area. RT # means Rock Type Number. Symbol of S_s for specific surface area.

6.1 Descriptions for the code:

Permeability k from Kozeny-Carman

Permeability k_{RT} from Rock-Type

Permeability k_i and Porosity ϕ_i which intersected between k and k_{RT}

6.2 Matlab codes:

% Written by Farizal Hakiki Soemarsono
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 % Updated: 2022 November 22

```

close all; clear all; clc;
Phi = 0.01:0.01:0.99;
Por = [1e-4 1e-3 0.005 Phi]; Por = Por';
tor = [1.3 2 4]; % dimensionless
ntr = length(tor);
rho = 2.6; % g/cc
Ss = [0.001 0.1 1 10 100]; % m^2/g
nSs = length(Ss);
c1 = 1e-12; % m6/cm6;
c0 = 9.869233e-16; % m2/mD
col = ['b', 'g', 'k']; %colour

NRT = 22; % Number of RockType you want
for i=1:NRT
    if i==1;
        b(i) = 0.4850;
        bB(i) = 0.4771;
        a(i) = 0.002.^(0.5-b(i));
        aB(i) = 0.002.^(0.5-bB(i));

    else
        b(i) = b(i-1)-0.02;
        bB(i) = bB(i-1)-0.02;

        a(i) = 0.002.^(0.5-b(i));
        aB(i) = 0.002.^(0.5-bB(i));
    end
end

figure(1)
for i=1:NRT
    x(:,i) = a(i).^2.*Por.^(1-6*b(i));
    kRT(:,i) = nthroot(x(:,i),1-2*b(i));
    semilogy(Por,kRT(:,i),'k'); hold on %Rock Type

%   xB(:,i) = aB(i).^2.*Por.^(1-6*bB(i));
%   kRTB(:,i) = nthroot(xB(:,i),1-2*bB(i));
%   semilogy(Por,kRTB(:,i),'-r'); hold on %Rock Type Boundary
end

%Kozeny-Carman
i=1;
for j=1:ntr
    for jj=1:nSs
        k(:,i) = c1/c0.*0.5.*(Por.^3)./((1-Por).*tor(j).*rho.*Ss(jj)).^2;
        semilogy(Por,k(:,i),col(jj),LineWidth=2); hold on
        xlim([-0.1 1]); ylim([1e-4 1e10]);
        xlabel('Porosity [ ]', 'FontSize', 15); ylabel('Permeability [mD]', 'FontSize', 15);
        i=i+1;
        %Each column = distinct Specific surface
        %Each 5 columns = distinct tortuosity, 5 = nSs
    end
end
end

```

```

[mk nk] = size(k);
%We set the number of rock type to 19, RT# = column
nRT = 19;
%Row = 1 to 15, each case for each Ss and tortuosity, nk = NRT*nSs cases
for j=1:nRT
    %Each RT at j
    for kk=1:nk
        %Each case at kk
        [xi,yi] = polyxpoly(Por,k(:,kk),Por,kRT(:,j)); hold on

mapshow(xi(xi==max(xi)),yi(xi==max(xi)),'DisplayType','point','Marker','o',Color='m',MarkerSize=9);
        Pori(kk,j) = xi(xi==max(xi));
        ki(kk,j) = yi(xi==max(xi));
    end
end
ax = gca;
ax.FontSize = 18;

figure(2)
%PGS Plot
%Data from Kozeny-Carman
i=1;
for j=1:ntr
    for jj=1:nSs
        Y(:,i) = sqrt(k(:,i)./Por);
        X(:,i) = k(:,i)./(1-Por).^3;
        loglog(X(:,i),Y(:,i),col(j)); hold on
        i=i+1;
    end
end

%Data from RT, Rock Typing Line
for i=1:NRT
    YRT = sqrt(kRT(:,i)./Por);
    XRT = kRT(:,i)./(Por.^3);
    loglog(XRT,YRT,'r'); hold on
end
xlim([1e-3 1e9]); ylim([1e-2 1e4]);
ylabel('sqrt(k\phi)','FontSize',15); xlabel('k\phi^3','FontSize',15);
ax = gca;
ax.FontSize = 18;

figure(3)
%Data from RT
%Rock Typing Line
for i=1:NRT
    YRT = sqrt(kRT(:,i)./Por);
    XRT = kRT(:,i)./(Por.^3);
    loglog(XRT,YRT,'r'); hold on
end

%Each colours = Distinct Tortuosity
Yi = sqrt(ki./Pori);
Xi = ki./Pori.^3;
coltor = ['ob', 'og', 'ok'];

```

```

% L=1:nSs;
% for j=1:ntr
%   loglog(Xi(L,:),Yi(L,:),coltor(j)); hold on
%   L=L+nSs;
% end
loglog(Xi(1:5,:),Yi(1:5,:),'ob'); hold on
loglog(Xi(6:10,:),Yi(6:10,:),'og'); hold on
loglog(Xi(11:15,:),Yi(11:15,:),'ok'); hold on

xlim([1e-3 1e9]); ylim([1e-2 1e4]);
ylabel('sqrt(k/phi)', 'FontSize', 15); xlabel('k/phi^3', 'FontSize', 15);
ax = gca; ax.FontSize = 18;

```

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